

Three dimensional breast cancer models for x-ray imaging research

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Abstract Breast cancer is by far the most frequently diagnosed cancer and the leading cause of cancer-related death among women worldwide. Despite technological advances, such as the digital mammography, the national screening programs, the introduction of the computer-aided design systems in clinical routine, screening and diagnosing of cancers hidden in breast dense parenchyma still remains a challenging task. The development, optimization and testing of new methods make an extensive use of both physical and computational cancer models. This paper addresses the methods used in generation of models of the breast cancer and their use in emerging x-ray breast imaging. Selected examples are presented from the current work of the biomedical engineering unit at Technical University of Varna, Bulgaria.

Keywords: *physical and computational breast cancerous models, breast imaging techniques*

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast Cancer is by far the most common incident form of cancer for women below seventy years of age with an estimated 1.4 million new cancer cases diagnosed in 2012 (23% of all cancers), and ranks second overall (10.9% of all cancers). Despite the indisputable successes of science in the cancer practice, morbidity and mortality rates are on the rise [1]. Early diagnosis is recognized as a critical factor that improves the chance of survival.

Despite technological advances, such as the digital mammography, the national screening programs, the introduction of the computer-aided design systems in clinical routine, screening and diagnosing of cancers hidden in breast dense parenchyma still remains a challenging task. New methods for early detection and correct diagnosis of breasts are needed. Dedicated machine learning systems may also assist in the detection and classification of the various types of the breast cancers. For this purpose, a large number of images containing different types of benign and malignant formations is required for their development and adjustment. The best approach in this case is to obtain simulated images with breast cancer. Thus, realistic three-dimensional (3D) computational models of the breast tumours are a requirement.

Tumour modelling is an important part of the realistic breast modelling. Tumour models are built to be incorporated into the existing or developed breast models to further allow performing of reliable virtual studies in the field of breast imaging and cancer detectability and diagnosis.

In general, tumour modelling can be performed through two basic approaches: by segmentation of breast lesions from 3D patient images and by using mathematical modelling. The first approach is applied on patient images obtained from breast tomosynthesis and Computed Tomography (CT) modalities, as well as, cadaver samples scanned at CT. The whole procedure usually includes filtering of the original images in order to reduce the noise, binarization of the area of the lesion, applying morphological operations to remove the remaining artefacts and region growing techniques to segment the lesion. This procedure may be also applied to high-resolution 3D microCT images of breast histology samples, followed by image segmentation and further characterizing: sizes, shapes, type of abnormality.

The second approach is the mathematical modelling, which offers the undoubted advantage to parametrically describe the 3D shapes or their generation. The use of mathematical modelling strongly relies on 3D random walks, followed by a set of image processing operations, which aim to deliver a solid based tumour. The level of simulated details is related to the required model complexity and heavily depends on the available computational power.

Researchers from the biomedical engineering unit at the Technical University of Varna has started the development of a database (MaXIMA Project Database) with computational models of breast tumours with irregular and speculated shapes. Research in this group is focused on the development of phase contrast breast imaging, which is a technique under development and may have the potential to add more information on tissue structure, as for example improvement in the visibility of edges. Successful investigation, however, is strongly related to the use of computer models and simulations in studying the feasibility of a given breast imaging technique. Since the model of this new imaging technique was already developed [2], the final key element needed to complete the simulation framework turns out to be the model of the cancer. The availability of such models is a powerful tool in the hands of biomedical engineers, physicians and physicists, which tolls are used in the development of new advanced technologies for precise definition of the boundaries of these cancers. These models offer a flexible, simple and cost-effective way to investigate and optimise different aspects of 2D and 3D breast imaging techniques in respect to cancer visualization and better detection, to perform accurate breast dosimetry, to investigate various computer-extracted texture features for the development of new CAD systems. This keynote speech will

address the methods used in generation of models of the breast cancer and their use in emerging x-ray breast imaging. Selected examples are presented from the current work of the biomedical engineering unit at Technical University of Varna, Bulgaria.

II. METHODS FOR MODELLING OF BREAST LESIONS

a region, containing the breast lesion is selected. A region growing method is applied to segment initially the breast lesion. Finally, post-processing is used to correct wrongly segmented tissue parts. Image processing operations are the following morphological operations: erosion, area opening, and dilation. The order of these operations is based mainly on the experience of the group, acquired after performing multiple tests in various order configurations.

Figure 1. Patient mammography data with a breast lesion: (a) cranio-caudal view (CC), and (b) planar mediolateral-oblique (MLO) image and (c) the respective tomosynthesis image.

Modelling of 3D breast lesions includes two basic approaches: (a) segmentation of breast lesions from patient images and (b) using mathematical modelling.

A. Segmentation of lesions from patient data

Three-dimensional breast images may be obtained from breast tomosynthesis and breast cone beam CT modalities [3], as well as, cadaver samples scanned at CT. The most available data are from breast tomosynthesis, which is currently a very promising techniques used to screen and diagnose dense breasts for low contrast breast lesions. An example of breast tomosynthesis image compared to planar mammography images of the same patient is shown in figure 1a-c.

A general outline of the approach for segmenting lesions from 3D breast imaging techniques is depicted in figure 2. The patient clinical data in the form of 3D image is the input for the algorithm. Before processing of data, a proper anonymizing of patient data is performed. Filtering of data is necessary to remove the artefacts due to the reconstruction algorithm. Then,

Figure 2. Outline of an algorithm for segmentation of lesions from breast 3D imaging techniques.

The proposed algorithm, recently reported by the group [4, 5], is semi-automatic as the initial selection of the region of the lesion and the choice of the seeds for the region growing process are performed interactively. Respecting the relevant ethical issues, all patient images obtained with Giotto Tomo and Siemens Mammomat were anonymized in advance. Breast cadaver images, obtained with Siemens Somatom Definition CT system, were exploited as well.

Figure 3. Screenshot from the presentation at RAD 2017 conference [5], presenting the approach. The main steps are: (a) original image, (b) after region growing, (c) after removing of artefacts and (d) final image.

Figure 4. Segmented breast cancer models as a result of applying the procedures outlined in figure 2 and figure 3.

The main steps of the algorithm applied on tomosynthesis images are shown in figure 3, while selected three-dimensional breast cancer models are shown in figure 4.

B. Modelling of lesions

The base of the algorithm is the generation of 3D random walks in a predefined space. Since the objects are voxel-based objects, the algorithm is modified to the so called nearest neighbour random walk. The basic steps in generating cancerous models are shown in figure 5 and include three major steps:

Figure 5. An algorithm for creation of irregular tumours, based on 3D random walk.

(a) The lesion is outlined in a 3D voxel matrix. The tumour size is function of the size of the voxel matrix marked as $M \times M \times M$ and the voxel resolution, res , defined by the user. Initially, the voxel values of the abnormality matrix are set to zero. The user assigns a number of random walks. This number is marked as $N_{brownian_runs}$. Each random walking process stops either at the matrix boundaries or when the assigned maximum number of discrete steps, N_{run_length} (number of voxels per walk) is reached.

(b) The random walk starts from the centre of the matrix and each step moves randomly to one of the neighbouring voxels, assigning it the abnormality elemental composition.

Figure 6. Three-dimensional images of computational solid irregular tumours, based on 3D random walk algorithm.

(c) The received powderish structure is converted to an abnormality with a solid geometry by applying further processing: averaging, dilation, erosion morphologic operations. In all operations, the structuring elements is the cube. For instance for the dilation operation, the repeating dilation is obtained with a larger cube size (5x5) followed by dilation using a smaller cube size (3x3), while averaging is reached with uniform averaging filter (arithmetic mean). Other morphological image processing methods, closing and morphological smoothing (opening followed by closing), have also cube as a structuring element. The size of the structure element as well as its shape can be changed. Closing and dilation operations were used also for binary image processing.

Selected examples are shown in figure 6. The choice of the parameters is critical for obtaining the realism of the simulated abnormality structure. In general, the use of more and longer walks results in realistic in shape breast abnormalities.

III. STUDIES WITH THE DEVELOPED LESION MODELS

Selected applications include database development, use in studies to optimize the parameters of breast tomosynthesis and use in training activities.

A. Database development

One of the goals of the Horizon 2020 EU project *Maxima* is to create computational breast models by using the two approaches for creation of lesions and place them in a database, which to be accessible by researchers working in this field. In short, the database 'Maxima' contains four tables, summarized as following:

- *patients* – it contains a list of records for 3D images and its attributes: name of the record, object of examination, imaging modality, data source, name of user, who adds the record, path to the images' directory, other additional information;
- *modalities* – it contains a list of imaging modalities with additional information;
- *medical sources* – it contains a list of data sources with corresponding information (name; country; city; name, e-mail, phone number of the contact person; other additional information);
- *users* – it contains a list of the users, who can use the application with the corresponding information (username; password (encrypted); level of access; personal information – name, e-mail, phone number, address, organization, other additional information).

All four tables are connected amongst each other by means of primary and secondary indexes to create the relations in the database. The database is currently in a process of filling its tables and will be opened to the scientific community after the end of the project.

Figure 7. Generated 3D breast model with an irregular mass. The abnormality is generated based on the 3D random walk approach.

B. Testing tomosynthesis

To test the visibility of the low contrast masses in breast

Figure 8. Compressing the generated 3D breast model with the irregular mass.

(a)

tomosynthesis and mammography we generated an anthropomorphic 3D model of the breast by using the dedicated *BreastSimulator* software [6]. The computational model is shown in figure 7 and it is composed of an external shape, glandular tree and an irregular mass, generated by using the random walk algorithm. The breast model is with a glandularity of 21%.

To be suitable for studies with breast imaging, the breast model was compressed and the resulted breast had a thickness of 4 cm, similarly to the mammography application (figure 8). Twenty six projection images in a tomosynthesis mode are simulated by using [6]. The incident beam energy was 20keV and the beam was monochromatic. Scatter and detector responses were not simulated. Distances from the source to the breast support table, where the phantom is placed, and to the detector surface, were 600 mm and 650 mm, respectively. The size of the images was 1200 x 1200 pixels. The pixel resolution was 0.085mm in each direction. A mammography image simulated at craniocaudal view is shown in figure 9a.

The 26 projection images are reconstructed with the FDKR software application, which is an application for reconstruction of tomosynthesis slices [7]. Figure 9b shows the reconstructed

tomosynthesis image at a plane where the lesion is detected. Clearly, the use of breast tomosynthesis brings on focus lesions, which are not visible on a planar mammography image.

C. Training purposes

Modelled lesions from the database have turned out to be very useful for training of the Medical Physics Experts. Specifically, they have been exploited in the two training courses (September 2015 and May 2017 in Varna <http://www.eutempe-rx.eu/>) by the participants of module 5 “The use of physical and virtual anthropomorphic phantoms for image quality and patient dose optimization” from the EUTEMPE-RX project (European Training and Education for Medical Physics Experts in Radiology). The main purpose of this course is participants to develop skills for the design and evaluation of anthropomorphic phantoms, as well as to design, manage, implement and evaluate virtual clinical studies with such phantoms, and to discuss and interpret the results of the virtual studies. The use of realistically modelled lesions was a necessary prerequisite in this challenging course. The following two work projects demonstrate the use of irregular lesion models carried out during this training.

Figure 10. Visualisation using (a) mammography and breast tomosynthesis modalities with (b) -9° to 9° arc and (c) -25° to 25° arc (images and text are from the work of Marius Laurikaitis and Anastasios Konstantinidis during the Eutempe-Rx course in Varna, 2015).

Figure 11. Slices and 3D Volume of the combined phantom (images and text are from the work of Rita Demou and Simona Avramova-Cholakova during the Eutempe-Rx course in Varna, 2015).

Work Project Example 1:

Marius Laurikaitis and Anastasios Konstantinidis were working on the development of computational breast phantoms to be used in a virtual study, which aimed to determine the potential of breast tomosynthesis for detectability of breast abnormalities, compared to conventional mammography.

They created a voxel-based phantom of size 641 x 357 x 175 voxels (0.3 mm voxels) composed from segmented CT slices. Then, an abnormality mass lesion of size 200 x 200 x 200 pixels was inserted into this volume. Conventional mammographic images and tomosynthesis images were simulated with the *BreastSimulator*, as the three dimensional imaging was modelled for two different gantry arcs: 18 degrees and 52 degrees, respectively and incident x-ray energy of 20keV. Reconstruction of tomographic images was realized via the dedicated software application FDKR.

Figure 10 shows simulated mammography (a) and tomosynthesis images using 10 planar projections (b) and 26 projections (c). The visual evaluation shows that breast tomosynthesis resulted in better visual detection of the abnormality compared to mammography case. In addition, tomosynthesis with larger arcs resulted in better mass visibility.

Work Project Example 2:

Rita Demou and Simona Avramova-Cholakova investigated whether dual-energy imaging improves detectability of breast abnormalities compared to conventional mammography. They used the same 3D breast matrix constructed from breast CT slices. Then, five microcalcifications with dimensions randomly sampled between 0.3mm and 1.2mm and an irregular mass were inserted in the phantom, as shown in figure 11. Then, they simulated four mammography images at 20keV, 50keV, 65keV and 80keV. Afterwards, they were properly weighted and combined into one image, called dual-energy image.

Figure 12 shows the visual assessment of the two different techniques, with an advantage of the dual energy images to improve the contrast of the microcalcifications and masses. They also concluded that the improvement of the contrast of the microcalcifications is more substantial while increasing energy difference of the dual energy images. Low contrast irregular masses are well visible when the second x-ray energy is above 65keV.

The limitations of the modelling approaches are related mainly to the different quality of 3D images provided by the different manufacturers. This implies sometimes modification of the algorithm developed in the filtering step of the approach outlined in figure 2. Another limitation is related to the low image resolution in z direction in case of limited arc 3D breast imaging. This may be overcome by using images of breast from Computed Tomography modality.

Figure 12. The 20keV planar projection and the dual energy images. Images are from the work of Rita Demou and Simona Avramova-Cholakova during the Eutempe-Rx course in Varna, 2015.

There are several benefits of this running research. The approaches of generation of cancerous models are currently used to generate computational breast cancerous models and to populate the dedicated database, which will be open to the scientific community at the end of the project. These models are intended for studies which aim is the development and optimization of x-ray breast imaging techniques. Another benefit is that the realistic computational breast cancerous models will be used to produce physical cancer prototypes to be introduced in physical breast phantoms, dedicated for x-ray imaging research.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Models play an important role in our life. In particular, they are very important when new technology is under development, testing and optimization. This paper addressed two methods used in generation of models of the breast cancer and their use in emerging x-ray breast imaging. The selected examples are from the current work of the biomedical engineering unit at Technical University of Varna, Bulgaria.

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REFERENCES

[1] J. Ferlay, I. Soerjomataram, et al. (2015). GLOBOCAN 2012 v1.0, Cancer Incidence and Mortality Worldwide: IARC CancerBase No. 11. Lyon, France: International Agency for Research on Cancer; 2013.

[2] K. Bliznakova, P. Russo, G. Mettivier, H. Requardt, P. Popov, A. Bravin, I. Buliev, A software platform for phase contrast x-ray breast imaging research, *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, (61): 62-74, 2015